

**CERTIFICATE
OF ACCEPTANCE**

This is to certify that the article authored by **Ismoilova Gulihayoxon Musajon qizi**, entitled “**Elektron kutubxona tizimi: kitoblarni boshqarish va foydalanuvchi statistikasi**”, has been reviewed and officially accepted for publication in International Online Multidisciplinary Conference: Science, Education & Future Trends Bulletin.

The editorial board acknowledges the scientific value of the submitted work and confirms its inclusion in the forthcoming issue of the journal.

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